

MICRO-ELECTRO-MECHANICAL VARIABLE BLAZE GRATINGS

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ABSTRACT

Two types of micro-electro-mechanical variable blaze gratings (VBGs) have been designed, fabricated, and tested. The gratings operate by adjusting the blaze angle of each slat so that the specular reflection of the incident light matches a particular grating diffraction order. The VBG blaze angle is adjustable with either electrostatic or thermal actuators. VBGs direct incident light in discrete directions, and are useful for steering light with beam diameters greater than 1 mm and power intensities greater than one watt.

Both electrostatic and thermal VBGs were constructed from gold and polysilicon using a surface micromachining process and tested with a 20 mW continuous wave HeNe laser operating at a wavelength of 632.8 nm. Optical selectivities (the ratio of power in the selected order to power in either of the non-selected adjacent orders) were determined for both electrostatically actuated and thermally actuated VBGs. The drive voltages for both types of gratings were measured for specific blaze angles and selected diffraction orders.

INTRODUCTION

Many potential applications of micro-electro-mechanical optical beam steering systems require optical beam diameters that are too large to fit on a single micromirror. Previously reported micromirror arrays have low fill factors (less than 50%), which may render them unsuitable for directing high power optical beams [1]. Some applications, such as digital laser radars, may benefit from an optical beam steering system that directs light in discrete directions. Variable blaze gratings (VBGs) have a high fill factor (up to 100% for non-normally incident light), and direct the majority of the diffracted light in a specific direction. VBGs are also suitable for spectrum analyzers that require multiple diffraction orders. The VBGs described in this paper were designed at the Air Force Institute of Technology and fabricated through the Multi-User MEMS Processes (MUMPs) sponsored

by the Defense Advance Research Projects Agency (DARPA) [2].

THEORY

A grating diffracts incident light into reflected orders. The direction of a particular order, θ_m , resulting from light incident at an angle θ_i is given by equation (1) [3].

$$\theta_m - \theta_i = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{m\lambda}{a} \right) \quad (1)$$

m is the order number, λ is the wavelength of the source, and a is the period of the grating. Variable blaze gratings operate by adjusting the blaze angle of each slat so that the specular reflection of the incident light matches a particular diffraction order. For normally incident light, the blaze angle γ_m to select a particular order m is half the angle of the order θ_m as measured from an axis perpendicular to the face of the grating. A torsion spring under the slat holds each slat parallel to the substrate. The electrostatic VBG is operated by applying a voltage between the slat and the bottom electrode, causing the edge of the slat opposite the torsion spring to be pulled down by electrostatic attraction. This action angles the slat towards the bottom electrode. The torsion spring returns the slat to its starting position when the voltage is removed. The thermally actuated VBG relies on the expansion of a polysilicon bar under the slat to push an edge of the slat off the substrate. This action angles the thermally actuated slat up from the substrate. In general, electrostatic VBGs have a higher operating frequency than thermally actuated VBGs. However, the maximum blaze angle of electrostatic VBGs is limited by contact with the substrate, while thermally actuated VBGs rotate above the substrate and are capable of a higher blaze angle.

FABRICATION

The gratings are constructed using surface micromachined thin films on a silicon wafer. MUMPs

offers three patternable layers of polysilicon, and two sacrificial layers of phosphosilicate glass on a base layer of silicon nitride. A top layer of gold is used as the reflective surface for each of the grating slats. Table 1 identifies the layer thickness for each of the films used in MUMPs. The order of the entries in Table 1 is consistent with the order in which the films are deposited on the silicon wafer substrate (silicon nitride layer is applied first). The gold is evaporated on to the device after all other layers have been deposited by low pressure chemical vapor deposition. The polysilicon layers and the substrate are highly doped with phosphorus (approximately 10^{20} atoms- cm^{-3}) to decrease electrical resistance. After fabrication, the device is "released" by removing sacrificial glass layers in a bath of 49% hydrofluoric acid for 2.5 minutes followed by a rinse in deionized water. The last step is an immersion in 2-propanol for 7 minutes to drive out residual water and reduce stiction.

TABLE 1. Structural and Sacrificial Layers Used in MUMPs [2].

Layer Name	Nominal Thickness (μm)
Nitride (silicon nitride)	0.6
Poly-0 (bottom polysilicon layer)	0.5
1st Oxide (sacrificial layer - phosphosilicate glass)	2.0
Poly-1 (middle polysilicon layer)	2.0
2nd Oxide (sacrificial layer - phosphosilicate glass)	0.75
Poly-2 (top polysilicon layer)	1.5
Metal (gold)	0.5

TEST SET-UP

Variable blaze gratings were tested with an attenuated 20 mW HeNe (632.8 nm) continuous wave laser in air and at room temperature. The light from the laser was positioned at a 45 degree angle to the face of the VBG, and in the plane of the diffracted orders as shown in Figure 1. A 300 mm lens was used to focus the laser spot on a single grating. The adjustable mirror and video camera were used to position and observe the laser spot on the die. The incident axis is perpendicular to the output axis.

Figure 1. VBG test set-up.

ELECTROSTATIC VBGs

Figure 2 shows a portion of an electrostatically operated VBG with $58 \mu\text{m}$ wide slats and a gap between adjacent slats of $2 \mu\text{m}$. This grating has 40 slats, each 2.4 mm long. After the grating has been released, the slats can be tilted with respect to the substrate by applying a voltage between the slats and the substrate. The tilt angle of the slat can be controlled until its lower edge is approximately one-third lower than its initial starting position. When the lower edge reaches this position, the slat becomes unstable, and is quickly pulled down to the underlying silicon nitride. This phenomenon is called "snap-through," and it results from countering a non-linear force (electrostatic attraction) with a linear force (the underlying mechanical spring) [4]. The silicon nitride layer is used to insulate the slat from the substrate so the device is not destroyed after snap-through. Figure 3 is a diagram of the electrostatically-operated VBG shown in Figure 1 with a portion of the Poly-2 and gold layers removed to show the underlying structure. A cross-sectional view of the device is shown at the top of Figure 3.

When sacrificial layers are removed, internal material stress causes the gold layer and its supporting Poly-2 layer to curl into a concave shape. For a $58 \mu\text{m}$ wide slat formed only out of Poly-2 and gold, curvature peak-to-valley distances of 200 nm are typical. By "stacking" or adhering the Poly-1 and Poly-2 layers over the majority of the slat, the curvature peak-to-valley can be reduced to a maximum of 127 nm. If a layer of the 2nd oxide is sealed in a cavity formed between the Poly-1 and Poly-2 layers, the curvature peak-to-valley can be further improved [5].

Figure 2. An electrostatic single-sided VBG with 58 μm wide slats.

In Figure 2, only the Poly-2 and gold layer are visible; the Poly-1 and Poly-2 are attached together everywhere except over the spring and support post.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the single-sided electrostatic VBG.

The single-sided VBG shown in Figure 2 is only capable of steering incident light over three orders. Figure 4 shows a portion of an electrostatic VBG designed to tilt on either side with 42 μm wide slats and a gap between adjacent slats of 2 μm . This grating has 50 slats, each 2.3 mm long. Two underlying Poly-0 electrodes are used to tilt the top Poly-2 slat on either side of its center torsion spring. Because the grating slat will touch a bottom electrode at snap-through, a current-limiting resistor is required to be in series with the electrodes to prevent destruction of the device. Table 2 lists the orders that the single-sided and

double-sided VBGs in Figures 2 and 4 can direct light into and the voltage required. All angles in Table 2 are the direction of the selected order measured with respect to the output axis shown in Figure 1. Because the gratings were designed with different slat widths, the diffracted orders are at different angular positions for each grating. The voltage measurements for the double-sided VBG were for the slat and the bottom electrode on one side and in series with a 1 K Ω resistor.

TABLE 2. Steering Orders and Voltages for Two Types of Electrostatic VBGs.

Order	Single-sided VBG degrees	Single-sided VBG volts	Double-sided VBG degrees	Double-sided VBG volts
-3	-	-	-2.5	61.2
-2	-	-	-1.6	48.5
-1	-	-	-0.8	29.6
0	0	0	0	0
+1	0.6	13.9	0.8	29.9
+2	1.2	22.9	1.6	48.9
+3	-	-	2.5	61.5

" - " = Not available on this device.

The slat tilt angle across the electrostatic grating is uniform. The optical selectivity, or the measure of power in the selected order divided by the highest power in an adjacent order was 13.4 for the single-sided VBG and 19.5 for the double-sided VBG. The optical selectivities were measured with the slats blazed to favor the second diffraction order.

Figure 4. An electrostatic double-sided VBG with 42 μm wide slats.

THERMALLY ACTUATED VBGs

A VBG driven by thermal actuators is shown in Figure 5. The width of the slats is 82 μm , and the gap between adjacent slats is 2 μm . This thermally actuated grating has 36 slats, each 2.5 mm long. Figure 6 is a diagram of the VBG in Figure 4 with the Poly-2 and gold layers made transparent to show the underlying structure. The slats are tilted by heating underlying 1.5 μm wide Poly-1 actuator arms with

electric current. The increase in temperature causes each actuator arm to expand, and lift an edge of the slat off the substrate. The fill-factor of the device was improved by using the gold on each slat as the electrical contact to and from the underlying thermal actuators. The slats are wired together in pairs using a Poly-0 connector. Current flows out on one slat, and returns on the adjacent slat after passing through thermal actuators under both slats. The measured electrical resistance of the entire device is 103.4 Ω .

Figure 5. A thermally actuated VBG with 82 μm wide slats.

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of the thermally actuated VBG.

If the actuator arms are heated close to their melting point, the arms will shrink below their initial length after the current is removed. This phenomenon is called "back-bending" [6]. Back-bending does not significantly reduce the total controllable range of motion produced by the actuators, but it does change the position of slats when no power is applied. Back-bending can be used to allow thermally actuated VBGs to steer over the -1 to +3 orders instead of the original 0 to +4 orders. The devices will be destroyed if excessive current passes through the actuator arms. Table 3 details the steering orders and corresponding voltages for the thermally actuated VBG shown in Figure 5 before back-bending. Back-bending occurred at 45 volts for this device, and the device was destroyed at 48.0 volts. The slat tilt angle across the thermal grating was also uniform. The optical selectivity for the thermally actuated VBG driven to select the second order was 27.9.

TABLE 3. Steering Orders and Voltages for a Thermally actuated VBG Before Back-bending.

Order	Thermally actuated VBG	
	degrees	volts
0	0.0	0.0
+1	0.43	6.1
+2	0.86	17.8
+3	1.30	30.2
+4	1.73	42.0

CONCLUSION

Tilt angle error and surface topology deviations resulting from the top Poly-2 and gold layers conforming to Poly-0 and Poly-1 structures had little

impact on optical selectivity. Figure 7 presents the measured optical selectivities for the electrostatic and thermally actuated VBGs set with a blaze angle favoring the second order.

Maximum incident optical power ratings for the devices have been estimated to be over one watt (at a wavelength of 632.8 nm), but have not been tested at present time. Also, frequency measurements have not yet been performed, however, other electrostatically-driven devices have been operated at frequencies above 10 KHz [7]. Thermally-driven devices have been operated at frequencies up to 300 Hz [8].

Future work on VBGs is directed toward increasing the number of selectable orders by improving actuator mechanisms. On-going Fourier finite element analysis is being conducted to model the slat surface. The goal of this analysis is to develop new slat designs with improved optical selectivities.

Figure 7. Measured selectivities of electrostatic and thermally actuated VBGs.

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